

AN ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR THE MECHANICAL RESPONSE OF DISCONTINUOUS COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Continuous-fibre reinforced composites are remarkably stiff and strong, but tend to fail in a brittle manner. This leads to conservative design, and makes traditional composites unsuitable for many damage-tolerant applications.

Discontinuous-fibre composites, albeit with more modest mechanical properties, offer lower production costs and improved manufacturability. Moreover, some short-fibre composites have a non-linear response [1], and cut-prepreg materials have been shown notch insensitive [2]. Detailed numerical analyses of unit cells in discontinuous-fibre composites [3] have suggested that it is possible to combine high stiffness, high strength and a ductile response in a single composite material.

This paper aims to further the understanding of the deformation and failure mechanisms in aligned discontinuous-fibre composites, and to study the potential of these materials for improved combinations of stiffness, strength and ductility. These challenges will be addressed by developing an analytical model for the response of discontinuous-fibre composites, taking into account the non-linear matrix response, statistical variability of local and global properties, and the quasi-brittle nature of final failure.

2 Model development

2.1 Multiscale modelling framework

Consider a discontinuous composite composed of stiff fibres of uniform length l_f dispersed within a soft matrix (Fig. 1); all fibres are aligned in the loading direction, with randomly located ends, and the overall fibre volume fraction is V_f . It is assumed that fibres carry the longitudinal stresses entirely, which are transferred by the matrix through shear. Fibres respond linearly up to failure, with strength

governed by a Weibull distribution; the non-linear behaviour and fracture of the matrix is also taken into account.

The response of discontinuous-fibre composites is governed by deformation and damage mechanisms operating at different scales. These are considered in the modelling framework as represented in Fig. 1:

- i. Macroscopic response of a discontinuous-fibre composite specimen, composed by stochastic variations of cross sections;
- ii. Tensile response of a cross section with length l_f , containing a critical Representative Volume Element (RVE);
- iii. Tensile response of a locally-periodic (in the longitudinal direction) RVE containing $n_a \times n_a$ fibres;
- iv. Tensile response of a single fibre with stochastic strength and 4 interacting neighbours;
- v. Shear-lag interaction between two neighbouring quarter-fibres in a square arrangement with randomly located ends;
- vi. Shear-lag response of the overlap region between two neighbouring fibre ends.

2.2 Shear-lag model for the overlap region between fibre ends

Consider the 1D representation of a shear overlap (of length $2L$) in Fig. 2, composed by two stiff quarter-fibres \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} (fibre cross section A_f , circumference C_f , equivalent thickness t_f and stiffness E_f), and an interlayer of soft matrix (thickness t_m):

$$t_f = \frac{\phi_f}{4} \quad \text{and} \quad t^m = \left(\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{4 \cdot V_f}} - 1 \right) \cdot \phi_f. \quad (1)$$

The matrix is assumed to have a generic piecewise linear constitutive response in shear (Fig. 2c), so that each *subdomain* i is characterised by its secant modulus $G^{[i]} \geq 0$.

Considering shear-lag stress transfer from fibres \mathcal{A} to \mathcal{B} , longitudinal stresses $\sigma^{\mathcal{A}}(x)$ and $\sigma^{\mathcal{B}}(x)$ are related to displacements $u^{\mathcal{A}}(x)$ and $u^{\mathcal{B}}(x)$, matrix shear deformation $\gamma^m(x)$ and stresses $\tau^m(x)$ by:

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{d\sigma^{\mathcal{A}}(x)}{dx} = \frac{d\sigma^{\mathcal{B}}(x)}{dx} = \frac{\tau_m(x)}{t_f} \\ \frac{d\gamma_m(x)}{dx} = \frac{u^{\mathcal{B}}(x) - u^{\mathcal{A}}(x)}{t_m} = \frac{\sigma^{\mathcal{B}}(x) - \sigma^{\mathcal{A}}(x)}{t_m \cdot E_f} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Putting $\Delta\sigma = \sigma^{\mathcal{A}} - \sigma^{\mathcal{B}}$, Eq. 2 can be combined as:

$$\frac{d^2\Delta\sigma(x)}{dx^2} = \frac{2 \cdot G^{[i]} \cdot \Delta\sigma(x)}{t_f \cdot E_f \cdot t_m}. \quad (3)$$

This differential equation defines the stress fields in each subdomain $[i]$ of the overlap (Fig. 2b), as well as its *process zone length* $l_{pz}^{[i]}$. Global fields are determined by imposing continuity of stresses and strains at the transitions ($x^{[j]}$) between adjacent *active subdomains* ($\{i, \dots, i+n\}$ in Fig. 2b) in the overlap.

This framework allows the calculation of the *complete length of combined process zones* (represented as $l_{pz}^{[i+1, \dots, i+n]}$) as well. Therefore, the evolution of the set of active subdomains $\{i, \dots, i+n\}$ with progressive loading is controlled by the relation between the combined process zone length $l_{pz}^{[i+1, \dots, i+n]}$ and the overlap half-length:

1. If $l_{pz}^{[i+1, \dots, i+n]} > L$, subdomains $\{i+1, \dots, i+n\}$ cannot develop fully within the overlap. Consequently, the central domain $[i]$ will be deactivated once $\gamma_m(L) = \gamma^{[i]}$, and the new set of active subdomains becomes $\{i+1, \dots, i+n\}$;
2. If $l_{pz}^{[i+1, \dots, i+n]} < L$, subdomains $\{i+1, \dots, i+n\}$ can fully develop within the overlap. Consequently, a new edge subdomain $[i+n+1]$ is activated once $\gamma_m(0) = \gamma^{[i+n]}$, and the new set of active subdomains becomes $\{i, \dots, i+n+1\}$.

This ability to define *a priori* the sequence of active subdomains in the overlap – despite considering a generic and non-linear matrix constitutive law – allows for calculating global stress and strain fields without an iterative process. The complete equilibrium solution is obtained by varying the matrix shear strain at the centre of the overlap within $\gamma_L \in [0, \gamma^{\max}]$.

For a staggered discontinuous composite with perfectly centred fibre ends ($L = l^f/4$, Fig. 2a), remote stresses and extensions are finally calculated as (subscript 0 represents $x = 0$):

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_L^\infty = \frac{\sigma^{\mathcal{A}}(0)}{2} \cdot V_f = \frac{\Delta\sigma_0}{2} \cdot V_f \\ \varepsilon_L^\infty = \frac{u^{\mathcal{A}}(0)}{2 \cdot L} + \int_{x=0}^{2L} \frac{\sigma^{\mathcal{B}}(x)}{2 L E_f} dx = \frac{\gamma_0 t_m}{2 L} + \frac{\Delta\sigma_0}{2 E_f}. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

These expressions neglect the presence of resin bridging regions between contiguous fibre ends, making them suitable for composites with high V_f and/or large l_f .

2.3 Interaction between neighbouring fibres with randomly located ends

Consider the local representation of a discontinuous composite with randomly located fibre-ends shown in Fig. 3a. Quarter-fibres \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} interact through 2 overlaps with lengths L_1 and L_2 (with $L_1 \leq L_2$) such that:

$$2 \cdot L_1 + 2 \cdot L_2 = l^f \quad \text{and} \quad L_1 \leq L_1^{\max} = l^f/4. \quad (5)$$

The interaction between \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} is therefore completely defined by the stochastic variable ρ :

$$\rho = \frac{2 \cdot L_1}{l^f} \quad \text{with} \quad 0 \leq \rho \leq 0.5. \quad (6)$$

Neglecting internal shear stresses within each fibre, the response of the $\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}$ interaction can be calculated by applying the previous shear-lag model to the overlaps L_1 and L_2 in series (since $\sigma_{L_1}^\infty = \sigma_{L_2}^\infty$):

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_\rho^\infty = \sigma_{L_1}^\infty = \sigma_{L_2}^\infty \\ \varepsilon_\rho^\infty(\sigma_\rho^\infty) = \rho \cdot \varepsilon_{L_1}^\infty(\sigma_\rho^\infty) + (1 - \rho) \cdot \varepsilon_{L_2}^\infty(\sigma_\rho^\infty) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Because the interaction is load-controlled, the shortest (weakest) overlap controls the strength of

the interaction, after which the longer overlap unloads elastically.

2.4 Stresses and failure of a fibre with 4 interacting neighbours and stochastic strength

Each individual fibre $f_{i,j}$ undergoes tensile stresses built through the interactions with its 4 neighbours (characterised by $\rho_{i,j}^h, \rho_{i,j}^v, \rho_{i,j+1}^h, \rho_{i+1,j}^v$, see Fig. 3b,c), which may lead to fibre failure. In order to account for the typical brittle nature of technical fibres, assume that their strength under uniform stresses is characterised by a Weibull distribution with modulus m and scale parameter σ_r at the reference length l_r .

When embedded in a composite, a discontinuous fibre undergoes a complex stress field; this depends on the local architecture, matrix response and fibre length, meaning that accurate probabilities of failure cannot be calculated analytically.

For the sake of simplicity consider that, for a given remote strain ε_f^∞ , fibre stresses are linear between zero (exact at the fibre ends) and a maximum σ_f^{\max} , estimated from its 4 interactions as:

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_f^\infty = \varepsilon_{\rho_{i,j}^h}^\infty = \varepsilon_{\rho_{i,j}^v}^\infty = \varepsilon_{\rho_{i,j+1}^h}^\infty = \varepsilon_{\rho_{i+1,j}^v}^\infty \\ \sigma_f^{\max}(\varepsilon_f^\infty) = \frac{2}{V^f} \frac{\sigma_{\rho_{i,j}^h}^\infty + \sigma_{\rho_{i,j}^v}^\infty + \sigma_{\rho_{i,j+1}^h}^\infty + \sigma_{\rho_{i+1,j}^v}^\infty}{4} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

It can be demonstrated [4] that, according to the WLT, the probability of failure for a fibre of length l_f under a linear stress field between 0 and σ_f^{\max} is given by:

$$F_L(\sigma_f^{\max}) = 1 - \exp \left[-\frac{1}{1+m} \cdot \frac{l_f}{l_r} \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_f^{\max}}{\sigma_r} \right)^m \right]. \quad (9)$$

This is used to assign a stochastic strength X_f to each individual fibre (see Eq. 11 in Section 2.5), so that failure occurs when (if) $\sigma_f^{\max}(\varepsilon_f^\infty) = X_f$; at this point, the fibre unloads instantaneously under displacement control, and $\sigma_f^{\max} = 0$ for any larger remote extension. It must be emphasised that failure of a single fibre does not affect its neighbours.

2.5 Stress-strain response of a locally-periodic cross section

Fig. 3a,b illustrates the RVE of the cross section in a composite specimen (dimensions $w_s^2 \times l_s$), with $n_f \times n_f$ fibres of length l_f .

The internal geometry of the cross section is determined by the end location of each fibre $\xi_{i,j}$ (normalised by l_r). This defines $n_f \cdot (n_f + 1)$ horizontal and vertical interactions according to:

$$\begin{cases} \xi_{i,j} = u, \quad u \sim \mathcal{U}(0,1) \text{ (uniform distribution)} \\ \rho_{i,j}^h = \min(|\xi_{i,j} - \xi_{i,j-1}|, 1 - |\xi_{i,j} - \xi_{i,j-1}|) \\ \rho_{i,j}^v = \min(|\xi_{i,j} - \xi_{i-1,j}|, 1 - |\xi_{i,j} - \xi_{i-1,j}|) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Due to the absence of interaction for fibres at the boundary of the cross section, $\rho_{i,j}^h = 0$ at $j = \{1, n_f + 1\}$, and $\rho_{i,j}^v = 0$ at $i = \{1, n_f + 1\}$.

The stochastic strength of each fibre, $X_{i,j}$, is defined from the in-situ strength distribution in Eq. 9:

$$X_{i,j} = \sigma_r \cdot \left[-(m+1) \cdot \frac{l_r}{l_f} \cdot \ln(u) \right]^{1/m}, \quad (11)$$

$$\{i,j\} = \{1 \dots n_f\}^2.$$

Assuming uniform fibre lengths and high fibre content, the local arrangement of fibre ends must be periodic along the longitudinal direction. This suggests that periodic boundary conditions can be used (neglecting variability amongst adjacent cross sections arising from the stochastic fibre strength). The nominal response of the cross section is thus calculated by imposing a uniform remote strain (ε^∞) to all fibres, whose stresses are averaged (following a global load sharing scheme) within the composite:

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon^\infty = \varepsilon_{f_{i,j}}^\infty, \forall i,j \in [1, n_f] \\ \sigma_{\text{nom}}^\infty(\varepsilon^\infty) = \frac{V^f}{2} \cdot \frac{\sum_{i,j}^{n_f, n_f} \sigma_{f_{i,j}}^{\max}(\varepsilon^\infty)}{n_f^2} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

2.6 Macroscopic response and final failure

The nominal response of the composite calculated in Eq. 12 does not allow for strain localisation within the cross section of a specimen. This corresponds to a fully ductile behaviour, which is far from realistic in fibre-reinforced composites.

In order to derive a better representation of the failure process in discontinuous-fibre composites, consider that the local material response varies stochastically, due to the randomness of fibre end-location and strength (Eq. 10 and 11). Under a progressively increasing remote stress σ^∞ , the composite will behave as follows:

1. The macroscopic response will be initially dominated by the nominal (ie average) behaviour. Locally weak regions of size a and strength $X(a) < \sigma^\infty$ will start failing and softening; but failure propagation will be arrested by the locally stronger neighbours;
2. As σ^∞ increases, each of the softening regions will grow and loose load-carrying capacity. Local cracks will form, surrounded by material which must necessarily be under stresses equal to its limiting strength;
3. As $\sigma^\infty \rightarrow \sigma_{crit}^\infty$, one of the softening regions will grow up to a size $a = a_{crit}$ such that its surrounding material is not sufficiently stronger to withhold strain localisation, and it becomes energetically more favourable for the material to fail through catastrophic crack propagation.

According to this sequence of events, final failure of discontinuous-fibre composites is governed by a combination of fracture mechanics and the local strength distribution of the material (Fig. 4a). This is characteristic of quasi-brittle materials, and requires considering the transition between brittle behaviour (governed by the fracture toughness) and ductile behaviour (governed by the strength).

Dugdale's strip-yield model [5] is a classical approach for the problem of fracture in non-linear materials. Considering a centre-crack (length $2a$) in a linear-elastic – perfectly-plastic material (with yield strength σ_y) under remote stresses σ^∞ , the equivalent stress intensity factor is derived as:

$$K_P(\sigma^\infty, a) = \sigma_y \sqrt{\pi \cdot a} \sqrt{\frac{8}{\pi^2} \cdot \ln \sec\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{\sigma^\infty}{\sigma_y}\right)}. \quad (13)$$

This relation can be extrapolated to other geometries to derive Failure Assessment Diagrams (as shown in Fig. 4b) [6]. This allows the energy release rate of a

non-linear material (J_P) to be calculated from the linear-elastic equivalent (J_E) and stress levels σ_y and σ^∞ as:

$$J_P(\sigma^\infty, a) = J_E(\sigma_y, a) \cdot \left[\frac{8}{\pi^2} \cdot \ln \sec\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{\sigma^\infty}{\sigma_y}\right) \right]. \quad (14)$$

Failure will therefore occur when $\sigma^\infty = X_{crit}$ and $J_P(\sigma^\infty, a) = \mathcal{G}_{crit}$, X_{crit} and \mathcal{G}_{crit} being respectively the strength and fracture toughness of the material.

Eq. 14 effectively bridges the two extreme cases of ductile (strength dominated) and brittle (toughness dominated) fracture:

- Dugdale's factor in Eq. 13 tends to σ^∞/σ_y when $\sigma^\infty \ll \sigma_y$. Consequently, a perfectly brittle material (finite \mathcal{G}_{crit} and $X_{crit} \ll \sigma_y$) will fail when $J_E(X_{crit}, a) = \mathcal{G}_{crit}$;
- Dugdale's factor in Eq. 13 tends to $+\infty$ when $\sigma^\infty \rightarrow \sigma_y$. A perfectly ductile material ($\mathcal{G}_{crit} \rightarrow \infty$ and $X_{crit} \approx \sigma_y$) will thus fail when $X_{crit} \rightarrow \sigma_y$.

This concept is adapted for the problem of final failure in discontinuous fibre composites. As represented in Fig. 4a, consider that the composite is characterised by a nominal strength $\sigma_y = X_{nom}$. Due to stochastic variability, one can define the weakest penny-shaped region (with radius a), which fails at the stress level $X_{crit}(a)$. Failure will occur when a sufficiently large region undergoes softening so that:

$$\sigma^\infty = X_{crit}(a_{crit}) \quad \wedge \quad J_P(X_{crit}, a_{crit}) = \mathcal{G}_{crit}. \quad (15)$$

For a penny-shaped crack,

$$J_E(\sigma, a) = \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \cdot \sigma \cdot \sqrt{\pi \cdot a}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{E_{nom}}, \quad (16)$$

where E_{nom} is the equivalent stiffness (accounting for plane strain and orthotropic behaviour). Combining Eq. 14-16, the criterion for final failure is defined as:

$$\mathcal{G}_{crit} = \frac{32}{\pi^3} \frac{1}{E_{nom}} X_{nom}^2 \cdot a_{crit} \cdot \ln \sec\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{X_{crit}}{X_{nom}}\right). \quad (17)$$

The value of X_{crit} and a_{crit} which satisfies Eq. 17 (calculated using moving windows in entire

stochastic realisations of composite specimens) is used as a cut-off in the nominal response calculated from Eq. 12. A simple method to estimate the fracture toughness $\mathcal{G}_{\text{crit}}$ is derived in the next section.

2.7 Fracture toughness of a discontinuous-fibre composite

The overall fracture toughness of a discontinuous fibre composite, required for Eq. 17, can be estimated from the contribution of debonding (subscript deb, toughness \mathcal{G}_m) and pull-out (subscript po, friction stress τ_μ). For each interaction between a pair of $1/4$ fibres (circumference C_f), the work dissipated is:

$$W_{\text{deb}} = \frac{C_f}{4} \cdot \mathcal{G}_m \cdot l_{\text{deb}} \quad , \quad W_{\text{po}} = \frac{C_f}{4} \cdot \tau_\mu \cdot \frac{l_{\text{po}}^2}{2}. \quad (18)$$

Normalising the energy dissipated by the projected area $A_f/(2 \cdot V_f)$, the toughness components are:

$$g_{\text{deb}} = \frac{2 \cdot V_f}{\phi_f} \cdot \mathcal{G}_m \cdot l_{\text{deb}} \quad , \quad g_{\text{po}} = \frac{V_f}{\phi_f} \cdot \tau_\mu \cdot l_{\text{po}}^2. \quad (19)$$

This expression assumes uniform debonding and pull-out lengths (l_{deb} and l_{po}). To account for stochastic fibre end-location and strength in a real discontinuous-fibre composite, the actual energy dissipated by debonding can be defined as:

$$\mathcal{G}_{\text{deb}} = \int_{l_{\text{deb}}=0}^{l_f/2} g_{\text{deb}}(l_{\text{deb}}) \ell(l_{\text{deb}}) S_L(l_{\text{deb}}) d l_{\text{deb}}. \quad (20)$$

In the previous expression, $\ell(l_{\text{deb}})$ is the probability density function for l_{deb} (uniform distribution within $[0, l_f/2]$). $S_L(l_{\text{deb}})$ is the fraction of fibres actually debonding, meaning they must survive the triangular stress field with $\sigma_f^{\text{max}} = C_f/A_f \cdot S_m \cdot l_{\text{deb}}$, where S_m is the matrix/interface shear strength. According to Eq. 9, this implies:

$$S_L(l_{\text{deb}}) = \exp \left[-\frac{1}{m+1} \cdot \frac{l_f}{l_r} \cdot \left(\frac{4 \cdot S_m \cdot l_{\text{deb}}}{\phi_f \cdot \sigma_r} \right)^m \right]. \quad (21)$$

Integrating Eq. 20 and following a similar procedure for the pull-out contribution, the overall toughness of a discontinuous-fibre composite is calculated as:

$$\mathcal{G}_{\text{crit}} = \frac{2 \cdot V_f}{\phi_f \cdot l_r} \cdot \left[2 \cdot \mathcal{G}_m \cdot \frac{l_0^2}{m} \cdot \gamma \left(\frac{2}{m}, \left[\frac{l_f/2}{l_0} \right]^m \right) + \tau_\mu \cdot \frac{l_0^3}{m} \cdot \gamma \left(\frac{3}{m}, \left[\frac{l_f/2}{l_0} \right]^m \right) \right], \quad (22)$$

with

$$l_0 = \frac{\sigma_0 \cdot \phi_f}{4 \cdot S_m} \cdot \left[\frac{l_r}{l_f} \cdot (m+1) \right]^{1/m}.$$

It must be noted that Eq. 22 is strictly valid for short-fibre composites only, as longer fibres will develop different dissipation mechanisms (debonding and pull-out from in-situ broken ends) not taken into account. For this reason, the actual toughness of composites with long fibres is assumed to saturate at the maximum value predicted by Eq. 22, as exemplified in Fig. 5a.

3 Results

The model developed in Section 2 was applied to predict the mechanical response of discontinuous-fibre composites with geometry and micromechanical properties as defined in Table 1. The effect of different matrices was studied considering the brittle and ductile cases as represented in Fig. 4b.

Fig. 6 presents intermediate results produced by the shear-lag model for the response of the overlap and the interaction between neighbouring $1/4$ fibres in a ductile matrix. Fig. 6a shows that the stress-strain response of short overlaps mimics that of the matrix, yielding low strength but large deformations. In contrast, long overlaps respond quasi-linearly up to the maximum stress, after which the load-bearing capacity is quickly lost. Fig. 6b illustrates the effect of stochastic location of fibre-ends, as the maximum load achieved in the staggered centred case ($\rho = 0.5$) is progressively lost for coordinated fibre ends ($\rho = 0$).

The predicted stress-strain response of composites with different fibre lengths is shown in Fig. 7. Comparing Fig. 7a and 7b highlights the effect of different matrices – which is very pronounced for the subcritical fibre case, but progressively reduced for increasing fibre lengths. It is also shown that the response of composites with long fibres is nearly linear, while composites with shorter fibres present some degree of non-linearity (depending on the matrix).

Fig. 8 shows how the mechanical response of discontinuous composites is affected by fibre length. Both the strength and the stiffness increase with fibre length – due to more effective load-transfer between neighbouring fibres – up to a plateau level – when fibre failure becomes dominant.

The evolution of maximum extension is more complex. As shown in Fig. 8c, the ductility increases as the fibre length is reduced from large values, due to the extra shear deformation mechanism occurring near fibre ends. However, below a certain threshold ($l_f \approx 0.8$ mm in Fig. 8c), the strength drastically reduces, causing a decrease in deformation as well. For even shorter fibres ($l_f < 0.2$ mm), the response of the composite becomes dominated by that of matrix – thus the extension will increase with decreasing fibre length in a ductile matrix, while it will keep on decreasing for the brittle case (also highlighted in Fig. 7).

Fig. 8d shows the percentage of failed fibres in the critical cross-section of the composite for different fibre lengths. The model is able to capture the transition (at $l_f \approx 0.8$ mm) between failure in a fibre-avoidance mode (in which matrix failure joins existing fibre ends) and in fibre-breakage mode.

4. Conclusions

A model for the mechanical response of discontinuous-fibre composites was developed. The formulation assumes a shear-lag stress transfer mechanism between neighbouring fibres, considering a generic response for the matrix. The stochastic distribution of fibre strengths and end-locations is taken into account. Final failure is determined by a criterion adapted from Dugdale's strip-yield model, combining the effect of finite strength, finite toughness and stochastic variability of local properties.

Predicted stress-strain curves showed a strong dependence on both fibre length and matrix constitutive law. Composites with very short fibres

are necessarily weak, while those dominated by fibre failure present low extension at failure. The model is also able to capture the critical fibre length for the transition between matrix and fibre dominated response.

The model suggests that composites with aligned fibres of intermediate length can provide a combination of high stiffness, high strength and moderate ductility. It also highlights the relevance of several effects – eg local and global variability, quasi-brittle failure and non-linear matrix response – in the response of discontinuous-fibre composites.

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Fig. 1: Scales in the model for discontinuous-fibre composites.

Fig. 2: Shear-lag model for overlapping region between fibre ends.

Fig. 3: Locally periodic (in the longitudinal direction) cross section with randomly located fibre ends.

a) Fracture mechanics of final failure (axisymmetric).

b) Failure criterion in the (J_E, σ^∞) domain.

Fig. 4: Modelling final failure in discontinuous fibre composites.

Table 1: Nominal inputs for modelling.

Geometry				Fibre				Interface
ϕ_f (μm)	V_f (%)	w_s (mm)	l_s (mm)	E_f (GPa)	X_r (MPa)	l_r (mm)	m ()	τ_μ^0 (MPa)
7	50	2	20	230	4000	10	4.5	10

a) Fracture toughness of the composites.

b) Matrix constitutive laws.

Fig. 5: Modelling inputs for predicting the response of discontinuous fibre composites.

Fig. 6: Response of overlaps and interactions (ductile matrix, no fibre failure, $l_f = 0.5$ mm).

Fig. 7: Stress vs strain curves for discontinuous composites, considering different matrices and fibre lengths.

Fig. 8: Effect of fibre length on the mechanical response of discontinuous composites with ductile matrix.